

INTEGRATING TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH CLASSROOM AND ITS EFFECT ON STUDENTS' MOTIVATION (A CASE STUDY AT SMPN 1 SUNGGUMINASA)

ANDI NURUL ANNISA BUDIMAN ¹, NASMILAH ² and ABIDIN PAMMU ³

^{1,2,3} Faculty of Cultural Sciences, Hasanuddin University.

Email: ¹an.annisabudiman@gmail.com, ²nasmilahunhas@gmail.com, ³abidinpammu60@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to find if technology integration affects students' motivation in learning English. This research used a mixed method design with the quantitative and qualitative analyses. The participants in this research involved 120 students from ninth-grade (IX) students of SMPN 1 Sungguminasa. In this research, the researcher adapted a self-developed questionnaire from Hashmiet al. (2018), and interview as the instruments for data collection. The data were analyzed using Likert scale data analysis for the questionnaire and qualitative data analysis for the interview. The result of this research indicated that technology integration does affect students' motivation in positive ways. The ways students perceive about technology integration in relation to their motivation varied. The findings confirm that technology integration in the English classroom affected students' motivation by making learning more enjoyable through presentation of various materials, making study time management more efficient, and providing easy access to unlimited learning resources. In addition, the students gave a positive opinion regarding technology integration in class, which show a mean value of 57.16. Most students, with a percentage of up to 85%, agree that the application of technology positively impacts their English learning motivation.

Keywords: Integration of Technology, Students' Learning Motivation, English Classroom.

1. BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Motivation is the mechanism that starts, directs, and sustains goal-oriented behaviours. Our desire for greatness and achievement serves as our motivation to take action. It is a strong force and a crucial element in our life path that comes from the natural desire of every human being to advance and improve. Sternberg (2000) asserts that a strong sense of motivation is essential for a student to be successful in school, as they need to put in the effort required to learn. A successful classroom and superior learning outcomes depend on an engaged teacher.

Teachers play an important role in setting the mood in the classroom. Nasmilah (2023) stated that learning English mostly exists in the classroom, and the following procedure is an action the students take to fulfil the teaching and learning objectives. The teacher's attitude and demeanour can set the tone for the entire class and significantly impact how the students interact and approach their learning. Since the Covid-19 pandemic forced the closure of nearly all educational institutions globally in March 2020, digital technology has been used increasingly in schools to assist teaching and learning (Scully et al., 2021). The unprecedented shift from face-to-face learning to home learning has had a profound impact on students and teachers across the world. They have had no choice but to adapt to technological methods over the past few years, where in its application, there are many difficulties that they have to face

for adjustments. According to Rahayu et al. (2022), Teachers needed clarification on explaining lessons in detail during online teaching and knowing which students understood. Besides that, students face problems. According to Haniva & Nurizzati (2021), they have difficulties in networking or inadequate internet signals due to learning during the pandemic. Even though there are difficulties in adapting to this dynamic system, there is a positive impact that students and teachers feel after they get used to this change. Bhat (2021) stated that the availability of audio-visual materials and equipment, as well as electronics and telecommunication media, enables teachers to obtain essential teaching materials and procedures.

Integrating technology tools and resources into routine teaching and learning activities is known as technology integration. It is a technique for utilizing technology to produce more purposeful, interesting, and efficient learning encounters. According to Puentedura (2013), technology integration is the process of developing and putting into practice a complete strategy for creating, using, and administering technological resources to support and improve educational activities. Utilizing computers, laptops, tablets, smart boards, digital cameras, voice recorders, and other digital media are all examples of technology enactment.

According to Lei & Zhao (2007), technology integration in the classroom is primarily meant to assist student learning. Technology can impact students' learning, but how it is applied will decide whether that impact is constructive or destructive. Additionally, technology can give students access to a wider variety of educational resources, foster collaboration and communication, and give instructors new tools for efficiently evaluating their students' learning progress and comprehension. According to Prensky (2001), technology is being used to improve and support the educational environment, especially in the transmission of teaching, the evaluation of student learning, and the growth of professional skills. Technology can also give educators and managers data-driven insights into students' learning, which can help them decide on content and teaching. According to Brooks-Young (2007), incorporating technology should enable instructors to assess students' learning through various methods. By creating pertinent learning experiences using technology, teachers can enhance education and give students a deeper understanding of their teaching topics. It can give instructors more chances for student participation and collaboration, enabling them to shift their attention away from lecturing and toward creating individualized learning experiences for each student. According to Ritonga et al. (2020), teaching English using the concepts of simple, useful, and comprehensible is most likely successful in gaining students' engagement.

Technology can be a potent instrument for motivating and energizing instructors in the classroom (Culatta, 2012). Teachers can involve their pupils more deeply when given access to technology and the tools to design interactive classes. Utilizing technology, educators can personalize and enhance learning for their pupils, improving learning results. According to Pammu et al. (2022), modern language education must incorporate technology by using the internet as a supplementary procedure for producing language learning. As a result, technology can also provide instructors with real-time feedback on student's performance, enabling them to more easily spot areas for development and modify their teaching strategies as necessary. As for supporting the learning process, supporting facilities and infrastructure are needed to

improve student learning results. Since 2016, regarding the Decree of the Director of Junior High School Development of the Directorate General of Primary and Secondary Education, Ministry of Education and Culture, regarding determining the first intermediate school level reference school, SMP 1 Sungguminasa has been appointed as a reference school. The existence of reference schools is expected to be a role model school for other schools in implementing an education quality assurance system that is implemented independently to meet or exceed national education standards (SNP) and have superior achievements in academic and non-academic fields. In the journey of SMP 1 Sungguminasa as a reference school. The school implemented a new program called Multimedia Class in 2019. This program requires students in the learning process to use laptops and the internet as learning media. Students in this class have the best grades when selecting to become students at SMP 1 Sungguminasa.

In 2020, the COVID pandemic caused difficulties in learning for students and teachers. Schools closed for over a month, and teachers created WhatsApp groups to facilitate learning. To reduce social distancing, schools used Zoom Meetings but faced difficulties. In multimedia classes, students taught other students and teachers how to use Zoom and Google Classroom. This situation lasted until May 2022, limiting face-to-face learning for two years. Teachers worked on a rotating schedule to reduce the spread of Covid-19. In June 2022, schools implemented blended learning to adapt to the Covid pandemic. The Ministry of Education has been improving students' and teachers' proficiency using the Internet and learning apps. Despite the limited duration of the learning process, students and teachers are happy with the limited interaction. Multimedia class teachers continue to teach students how to use the internet and learning applications, ensuring a seamless learning experience for both students and teachers. In January 2023, schools resumed face-to-face learning for the first time since the COVID pandemic began. They no longer dispute after-school hours and use Zoom for learning processes. As a result, schools provide facilities to support blended learning, such as printing services, using Google Classroom, and increasing projectors. The free quota for students to support the learning process from home has been stopped. This shift in learning methods is expected to help students adapt to the endemic situation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous studies have investigated the impact of technology integration on students' motivation, primarily focusing on elementary, high school, or college students. Previous studies are closely related to the current research. Hashmi et al. (2018) studied the impact of ICT on university undergraduate motivation in Rawalpindi City. A survey questionnaire collected data from 340 students, and descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the findings. The study found that ICT positively impacted student motivation, learning, knowledge retention, and understanding. Serado et al. (2020) conducted a study at Davao Del Norte State College, Philippines, to determine student motivation in using technology as a learning tool. The research aimed to determine if there was a significant relationship between technology and its impact on student's motivation in education. The findings showed that technology significantly influences students' motivation in learning, making it easier for teachers to instruct

and motivate students and making complex concepts easier to understand. Francis (2017) investigated the relationship between technology integration and student motivation in classroom-based learning. The study found that using technology for pedagogical goals or accommodating accommodations, such as Individual Education Plans (IEPs) or 504 plans, motivates pupils. Modern teachers must consider students' desire to learn and the impact of technology on inclusive education.

Technology integration in education involves utilizing technology to improve learning settings, such as classrooms, by enabling students to complete computer assignments. It also involves integrating platforms to connect different SaaS (Software as a Service) programs, databases, and applications enhancing data quality and access for faculty and staff. This process aims to enhance student learning and support the integration of technology resources and tools in educational activities (Warschauer, 2003). Integrating technology into education involves using various instruments to improve student's learning experiences. Virtual classrooms and individualized teaching opportunities are introduced to encourage engagement and adapt to individual needs. While some may believe it will cost too much, it can benefit students without owning tablets or computers. Technology can involve auditory and visual learners during group teaching and be used for data collection, storage, processing, and presentation. The increased ability to acquire and exchange information is the main benefit of contemporary technology in education (Davies & West, 2013).

Motivation is an internal process that drives individuals to act based on their goals, desires, and needs. It can be intrinsic or extrinsic and come from positive and negative sources. Motivation is crucial for determining success or failure in various activities, such as mastering a second or foreign language. It provides an objective and direction for an individual to achieve, which is essential for success. Motivation is influenced by various factors, such as confidence in one's abilities, the level of difficulty, and the motivation to focus on the goal. Living in a safe and secure environment, working with interesting topics or materials, and having the opportunity to make decisions and participate in activities can also contribute to motivation. Overall, motivation is a crucial factor in determining success or failure in various aspects of life.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to achieve the research question, the research design used by the researcher in this research is mix method. *Mix method* is a research method which combines elements of both qualitative and quantitative research. It is used when researchers seek a more comprehensive understanding of a research problem, often by looking at the phenomena from multiple perspectives. The method involves collecting quantitative and qualitative data, analyzing the data separately, and then combining the results for an overall view of the research problem. Mix method approach is selected as the research design by combining qualitative and quantitative data collection procedures for two main reasons. First, Creswell (2012) states mixed method utilizes qualitative and quantitative research strengths. Malik & Hamied (2014) stated that the research will get a better understanding when combining both qualitative and quantitative data. The participants of this research are 120 students in grade 9th who carry out

the learning process in EFL Classroom. SMPN 1 Sungguminasa is the place to conduct this research. This school located in Somba Opu, Gowa, South Sulawesi. SMP Negeri 1 Sungguminasa is the first junior high school established in Gowa. The researcher is interested in conducting research at this school because it is one of the reference schools in Gowa.

This research used two methods to obtain data from the beginning to the completion of the teaching-learning process. The researcher used a mixed-method technique to conduct this research to offer flexibility and a hands-off approach to data collection. The data for this research were gathered through questionnaires and interviews. Roopa & Rani (2012) stated that a questionnaire is a set of questions designed to gather data on a particular topic from individuals to gain useful statistical information. According to Sugiyono (2009), the interview is a process of exchanging information between two people through questions and answers that result in communication about a certain topic. The researcher adapted self-developed structured questionnaires from Hashmi et al. (2018). The questionnaire consists of 15 statements that have been pilot tested, validity, and reliability from the experts. This questionnaire investigates the role of technology integration in motivating and learning students. The researcher adapted Interview guidelines from Adilah (2021). This interview measures the use of technology integration in class in relation to students' motivation in learning. After collecting data, the researcher analyses it with the following steps. Classifying and counting how many responses strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree from the entire questionnaire. The quality of each response using Likerts' Scale is as follows:

Table 3.1: Category Value Table

Category	Score
Strongly Disagree	1
Disagree	2
Neutral	3
Agree	4
Strongly Agree	5

Analyzing the percentage by using formula as below:

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100\%$$

P = Percentage

f = Frequency

N = Amount of sample

Find out the mean score of each respondent by using mean score formula below:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

\bar{X} = mean score of each respondent

X = Total score of each respondent

N = The total number of statement

Making the categories of each respondent result based on the evaluation criteria for Likert Scale:

Table 3.1: Range of Answer Options of the Likert scale

Range		Agreement	Classification
190 – 225	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Positive
154 – 189	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	
118 – 153	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Neutral
82 - 117	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative
45 – 81	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	

Based on Table 3.1, making categories by classifying the respondent's frequency results with the same score. After that, describe respondent results about technology integration to their

The researcher also used qualitative analysis for processing interview data. (1) Reading the transcripts. Browse through all transcripts as a whole. Make notes about impressions. Read the transcripts one by one very carefully. (2) Labeling relevant pieces. Label relevant words, phrases, sentences, or sections. (3) Decide which most essential codes and create categories by combining several codes. Create new codes by combining two or more codes. Keep the codes that are important and group them. (4) Label categories and decide the most relevant and how they are connected. (5) Describe the connection between them. The categories and connections are the main results of this research. Draw a figure to summarize the results. (6) Write up the results.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

The findings and discussion of data were collected through questionnaires and interviews with 120 respondents from March 6th to March 17th, 2022. This research was conducted without treatment or participation in class. The study found that students' opinions on integrating technology in English classrooms on learning motivation varied. This research aimed to understand how technology integration affects students' motivation to learn English. Relevant results were obtained from the cited related resource.

4.1 Result of Questionnaire

From the distribution of the questionnaire, it can be seen that the composition of respondents according to gender is presented in table 4.2 below:

Table 4.1: Gender of Respondents

No	Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Female	64	53.34
2	Male	56	46.66
	Total	120	100

Based on the processed data regarding the composition of respondents in Table 4.1, most respondents are female students, with a percentage of 53.34% and male students, with a

percentage of 46.66%. Based on the questionnaire result, it was shown that integrating technology in the English classroom affects each student differently. The following table shows the mean and standard deviation of the questionnaire:

Table 4.2: Mean and Standar Deviation

N	Mean	Standar Deviation	Range of Answer
120	57.16	7.819	3.81

This research adopted a questionnaire from Hashmi et al. (2018), assessing students' motivation in the English classroom. The questionnaire used a five-point Likert scale, with a mean score of 57.16 and a range of 3.81. The results showed that technology integration positively affects students' motivation in the English classroom. The overall score is classified as positive, indicating that technology integration positively impacts students' motivation.

Table 4.3: Subjective Experience Classification

Range	Frequency	Percentage	Agreement	Classification
4.21 – 5.00	20	16.67	Strongly Agree	Positive
3.41 – 4.20	82	68.33	Agree	
2.61 – 3.40	14	11.67	Neutral	Neutral
1.81 – 2.60	3	2.5	Disagree	Negative
1.00 – 1.80	1	0.83	Strongly Disagree	
Total	120	100		

The students of SMPN 1 Sungguminasa responded to a questionnaire about integrating technology in English classrooms and its impact on their motivation. The responses were divided into three groups: positive, neutral, and negative. The average range point for positive responses was <5.00, while neutral responses were <4.20 and <3.40. Negative responses were <2.60 and <1.80, respectively. The results indicate diverse opinions on integrating technology in English classrooms.

This research used a questionnaire consisting of 15 adapted items. The following is the classification of the number of statements obtained from the overall student response and interpreted into the Likert scale range of answer values.

No	Statements	Total	Range
1	ICT makes course more interesting and lively	514	4.3
2	ICT helps student to complete a piece of work that sometimes would be difficult to complete without it	494	4.1
3	Students pay more attention when lessons involve the use of ICT.	376	3.1
4	Using ICT makes topics visually attractive.	472	3.9
5	By using ICTs student can work longer without losing concentration.	388	3.2

The statement No 1 ICT makes course more interesting and lively calculated 514 total score with 4.3 range of answer. The statement No 2 ICT helps student to complete a piece of work that sometimes would be difficult to complete without it calculated 494 total score with 4.1 range of answer. The statement No 3 Students pay more attention when lessons involve the use

of ICT calculated 376 total score with 3.1 range of answer. The statement No 4 Using ICT makes topics visually attractive calculated 472 total score with 3.9 range of answer. The statement No 5 By using ICTs student can work longer without losing concentration calculated 388 total score with 3.2 range of answer.

No	Statements	Total	Range
1	Working with ICT is a fun for the students.	475	4
2	ICT helps students to explore learning resources.	515	4.3
3	ICT is helpful in motivating students.	461	3.8
4	ICT can enhance student's participation and feedback to teachers.	417	3.5
5	ICT help to generate a pleasant atmosphere in the classroom.	424	3.5

The statement No 1 Working with ICT is fun for the students calculated 475 total score with 4 range of answer. The statement No 2 ICT helps students to explore learning resources calculated 515 total score with 4.3 range of answer. The statement No 3 ICT is helpful in motivating students calculated 461 total score with 3.8 range of answer. The statement No 4 ICT can enhance student's participation and feedback to teachers calculated 417 total score with 3.5 range of answer. The statement No 5 ICT help to generate a pleasant atmosphere in the classroom calculated 424 total score with 3.5 range of answer.

No	Statements	Total	Range
1	The use of ICT improves student's grades.	439	3.7
2	The use of ICT enhances quality of education.	449	3.7
3	ICT provides students freedom of expression.	461	3.8
4	The use of ICT develops more interest among the students	456	3.8
5	ICT provides quick and easy access to materials needed by students.	519	4.3

The statement No 1 The use of ICT improves student's grades calculated 439 total score with 3.7 range of answer. The statement No 2 The use of ICT enhances quality of education calculated 449 total score with 3.7 range of answer. The statement No 3 ICT provides students' freedom of expression calculated 461 total score with 3.8 range of answer. The statement No 4 The use of ICT develops more interest among the students calculated 456 total score with 3.8 range of answer. The statement No 5 ICT provides quick and easy access to materials needed by students calculated 519 total score with 4.3 range of answer.

4.2 Result of Interview

Interviews were conducted with ten students as participants. Interviews were conducted after the researchers took the questionnaire data. The ten participants are students who are willing to be recorded and documented. Students are free to answer questions from researchers according to their respective opinions. The following points were found in this research interview.

- The Integration of technology makes learning English more enjoyable.

The interview results found that some students liked it when the teacher taught the class with the help of technology. The media technology commonly used by teachers is a projector that presents PowerPoint slides. According to students, using it makes them more interested in learning because it is visually attractive. *It helps the students to understand the concepts*

better. This point was proven from the data obtained in the interview below:

(Participant 9)

"It is interesting if the teacher presents using PowerPoint because there are pictures. I learn visually."

"Menarik kak kalau guru presentasi pake powerpoint karena ada gambarnya karena saya belajar dengan visualiasi."

- Time becomes more efficient with the application of technology.

Technological media devices such as smartphones and laptops cannot be separated in the current era, and education is no exception. Students can take pictures of the teachers' notes and record the classes on their smartphones. Students can edit and customize their homework while using laptops for writing tasks. Based on the interview results, some students understand how to operate technology media in the form of cellphones and laptops in general. This point was proven from the data obtained in the interview below:

(Participant 1)

"Proficient enough, sis"

"Cukup mahir kak"

(Participant 6)

"Yes I can. Like use Microsoftword"

"Iya kak bisa. Pakai word juga bisa kak"

- Easy access to unlimited learning resources

The internet is frequently used for educational purposes to obtain information, do research, or increase understanding of various disciplines. The internet is vital for schooling. Everyone today, especially students, chooses Google for their questions, issues, or uncertainties. Google and other well-known search engines. This point was proven from the data obtained in the interview below:

(Participant 3)

"Easy. Because it is easy to find answers, especially on the internet."

"Mudah. Karena gampang cari jawabannya apalagi kalau di internet ji."

- The Integration of technology in the classroom has a positive effect on increasing learning motivation.

Student learning motivation can increase because the learning atmosphere is more engaging. The teacher applies technological media in his class so that students will feel energized by the traditional teaching and learning process, which is focused on the teacher as the only source of information in the classroom. This point was proven from the data obtained in the interview below:

(Participant 8)

“...It is important for the application of technology in class, especially for teachers, so that classes are more enjoyable because we are used to students being sleepy during the day.”

“...Penting untuk pengaplikasian teknologi dikelas apalagi untuk guru supaya kelas lebih menyenangkan karena biasa kita siswa mengantuk di siang hari.”

- Strong self-motivation and time management skills are essential for e-learning.

One of the leading causes of students failing to finish online courses is still needing self-motivation. In contrast to online learning, which offers many conveniences but has students struggling to manage their own time, conventional classrooms contain a variety of forces that continually drive students towards their learning goals. This point was proven from the data obtained in the interview below:

(Participant 6)

"In terms of learning, I choose face-to-face offline. Offline tasks are manageable. However, overall the learning experience was interesting. Unforgettable. Nevertheless, I prefer the current situation if I want to return to studying online."

“untuk belajar saya pilih offline tatap muka. Kalau offline tugas tidak menumpuk. Tapi secara keseluruhan sih kak pengalaman belajar dulu itu menarik. Tidak bisa dilupa. Tapi untuk kembali belajar online sih saya lebih pilih waktu sekarang”

- Online learning may result in social exclusion for students.

Online learning methods in education often lead to silent reflection and social isolation, causing mental health problems such as boredom, increased stress, anxiety, and negative thoughts. The lack of human interaction and social exclusion can lead to boredom, as Bloomfield & Kennedy (2006) assert, which can lead to psychotic symptoms. This is supported by the data obtained in the interview.

(Participant 1)

"I choose offline so that I can mingle with other friends. Because at home I feel bored. When studying online I usually don't understand."

“Kalau saya sih offline. Supaya bisa berbaur sama teman teman yang lain. Kalau dirumah bosan. Kalau online saya suka tidak paham”

- The integration of technology media is not evenly distributed in each class

At SMP 1 Sungguminasa, multimedia classes are offered in each grade, with more complete technological devices supporting teaching and learning processes. This uneven technology learning media affects English teachers' ability to apply it effectively. If a class is not multimedia-supported, teachers must bring projectors and speakers, which can waste lesson time. Students in multimedia classes also understand more about using laptop devices for learning, as they have a better understanding of technology compared to regular classes:

(Participant 10)

"Yes. I was learning in grade 7 during the pandemic because I was in a multimedia class, so I could not help but have to study. I used to be taught by seniors here and bring my own laptop."

"Iye kak. saya baru belajar dikelas 7 waktu pandemic karena saya kelas multimedia jadi mau tidak mau harus belajar. Dulu diajar sama kakak senior disini bawa laptop sendiri."

- The ability of English teachers to use media technology in the learning process is not the same.

It is essential in the current era for teachers as educators to be proficient in using technological devices to keep up with the times. Teachers need to make their teaching methods as attractive as possible so that students in their class are motivated to learn and can fulfil their learning engagement. Teachers' ability at SMPN 1 Sungguminasa is different in using technology. Especially English teachers, not all are proficient in using it. In schools, several teachers with a range of ages are different from each other and teach at different grade levels. This statement was proven from the data obtained in the interview below:

(Participant 10)

"Depends if needed. English subjects still need to be applied better. But for other subjects, yes."

"Tergantung sih kak kalau diperlukan. Kalau pelajaran bahasa inggris sendiri masih kurang diterapkan. Tapi kalau mata pelajaran lain iya."

Discussion

The study reveals that technology integration positively impacts students' learning motivation, as evidenced by Hashmi et al.'s (2018) findings. A self-developed questionnaire revealed that students find mobile devices to make learning enjoyable and interesting. The highest-ranking statement, "ICT makes courses more interesting and lively," supports the research objective, indicating that technology enhances motivation, engagement, and interest, ultimately leading to a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The 15th statement of ICT provides quick and easy access to materials for students, with a high result among other statements. Student interviews show unlimited learning resources, making the Internet a valuable tool for students. The Internet allows them to find answers and access their needed resources quickly. University students use online resources for research and learning, benefiting from free access to these resources. Overall, students have easy access to the Internet as a valuable resource.

The study found that students pay more attention to ICT lessons but dislike remote classes. This is consistent with student interviews and interviews. Students prefer studying offline at school compared to online learning from home. This aligns with Sharma et al (2022) findings, which show that students can develop close relationships with classmates with similar intellectual interests outside the classroom. Online classes are challenging to achieve this bonding experience, making offline classes preferred over online ones. Peer interactions between students, teachers, and other students are often better. Technology significantly impacts student motivation, engagement, and interest in education. As demonstrated by Haleem

et al (2022) analysis, technology integration makes learning more enjoyable. Advancements in digital technology have simplified life and enhanced information presentation, making learning more engaging. Students perceive technology as a pleasant experience, particularly during the pandemic. The Zoom application is an example of this, as students find it exciting and engaging. However, improvements in implementation and learning engagement are needed.

The study reveals that students perceive technology's application positively in class, positively impacting their motivation. This aligns with chart 4.1 of student population classification and Francis' (2017) findings, which suggest that students feel motivated when technology is used specifically for educational or general objectives. Students generally accept the use of technological media in the classroom but find online learning boring and dependent on the teacher's leadership. This is due to internal and external factors, such as a lack of motivation and time management skills. Strong self-motivation and time management skills are essential for e-learning success, as noted by Foltýnek & Motycka (2009). Strong self-motivation is crucial for achieving student learning objectives in e-learning. A teacher's ability to operate technology is crucial for online learning success. Student interviews show that learning processes may not align with the current technology landscape without this ability. Effective technology utilization in education can boost output and enhance teaching methods, as Erişti et al. (2012) noted.

The analysis reveals that technology media in the classroom benefits students, but it is essential to recognize that some students may find it challenging to apply technology. Some prefer using a laptop for assignments, while others find printing difficult. Carstens et al (2021) found that some students who use technology score lower on motivation than those who complete projects without technology. Technology can increase student motivation, but it is crucial to consider individual differences and ensure proper training for students and teachers.

5. CONCLUSION & SUGGESTION

Conclusion

This research aimed to describe the integration of technology and its effect on students' motivation. The result shows that the integration of technology positively affects students. Based on the findings, the questionnaire results are classified into three classifications: positive, neutral, and negative. Of the classified as positive with 85%, 14 students were classified as neutral with 12%, and four students as negative with 3%. It can be concluded that it is proven there are 102 students' classified as positive with 85%, 14 students' classified as neutral with 12%, and four students' classified as negative with 3%. Thus, most students felt that the application of technology positively affected their learning motivation.

The findings also revealed how students perceive technology integration in their learning motivation. It proved by several perspectives of students regarding the case where technology affected students' motivation in learning. There are several types of integration technology emerged in this research which are; teacher teaching using a projector and speaker in class, students using internet assistance in doing assignments, students understanding how to use

laptops and smartphones, using the Zoom application when studying online from home, and collect assignments using Google classroom. From above, the way technology integration affects student learning motivation is; it makes learning more enjoyable by presenting various materials, making study time management more efficient for students, and providing easy access to unlimited learning resources. Most students felt that the application of technology positively affected their learning motivation in English class. However, several things need to be underlined. Students must accept the concept of applying technology in the classroom: online learning from home. Likewise, students do not hate the concept as a whole but think that the experience is exciting and memorable, but they do not want to apply it again if the application is still the same as before.

Suggestion

The researcher suggests that students should be cautious when using technology, as it can negatively affect self-motivation and learning objectives. Teachers should be able to effectively use technology in their classrooms to ensure students' success. They should also innovate to create comfortable and enjoyable learning environments. Schools should improve technology facilities, such as installing projectors and built-in speakers and installing wifi throughout the school area. Limiting data usage and requiring students to enter their identification numbers can help prevent repeated use. Research on teachers' perspectives on technology's application to motivation is recommended, as it can provide valuable insights into student learning motivation and teacher teaching motivation. This research is particularly relevant in Indonesia, where it is needed at the secondary school level.

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